

IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE AND PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance, effectiveness and advantages of using interactive and pedagogical technologies in primary classes.

INTRODUCTION

For an elementary school teacher, it is important not so much to enrich a child with knowledge, but to teach him to independently obtain knowledge, be able to listen and engage in dialogue, participate in a collective discussion, unite with peers, build productive interaction and cooperation with peers and adults. It is important to teach children to learn not only today, but throughout their lives. This is the global task of a modern teacher.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It was important for us to find such educational technologies, the use of which in the educational process will interest, involve all students in the lesson, will contribute to the activation of cognitive activity, the effective assimilation of new knowledge and ways of obtaining it, that is, they will provide "ability to learn."

As a result, we have mastered interactive learning technologies. According to I.A. Winter, interactive training is training built on:

- interaction of the student with the learning environment and environment;
- psychology of human relationships and interaction;
- organizing comfortable learning conditions in which all students actively interact with each other [3].

Interactive learning methods are focused on cooperation between participants in the educational process, developing the student's active position, teaching the child "the ability to act," "the ability to be," and "the ability to live" [1].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An important component of such lessons is the dynamic activity of children. During the task, they are in motion, choosing a comfortable position for themselves, which allows the child to feel comfortable, regulate their activity mode, and therefore become less tired from

the academic load. Children do not immediately begin to communicate with each other, jointly search for a way to solve a given problem, overcome conflicts, etc. But gradually children accept new educational conditions and begin to cooperate with the teacher and peers. Skillful organization of student interaction in the classroom using interactive technologies becomes a powerful factor in increasing the effectiveness of educational activities as a whole. From our work experience, we consider the following to be the most effective interactive techniques and methods.

- **Reception “Bus stop”**

This technique is effective at the stage of mastering knowledge and a new way of acting in a lesson or extracurricular activity. The essence of the method is that children are divided into three teams that move from stop to stop. Each stop has one task, which is carried out by teams in turn. A certain time is given to complete the task; the team can manage to complete it completely, correctly or not completely and with errors. When another team comes, it performs this task again, using the experience of the previous team. There is mutual checking, children correct each other’s mistakes, if any, analyze, coordinate the results, etc.

- **Technique “Conceptual table”**

This technique is used at the stage of introducing new knowledge and methods of generalizing it. The table is based on a matrix that allows for a comparative analysis or a comprehensive assessment. The “Conceptual Table” technique is used when children of different subgroups compile a table, then they combine to analyze the opinion of each subgroup and choose the one that is most relevant to the whole group.

For example, during a literary reading lesson in 3rd grade, students wrote characterizations of the sisters based on the fairy tale “Three Sisters.” Each subgroup filled out a table taking into account the characteristics of the actions of the sister they chose. Then the children all together compared the resulting images, in the process of comparative analysis they added important characteristics to the sisters’ portraits, changed the description, etc. In the dialogue, children generalized information, enriched it with new examples, and came up with new situations using their social experience.

- **Carousel technique**

The “Carousel” technique is used to consolidate knowledge. During the lesson, we ask the children to divide into two unequal subgroups. Children form two circles: internal and external. The inner ring is motionless, and in the outer ring, students change every 30 seconds at the teacher’s signal and perform various tasks pre-planned by the teacher. The tasks can be different: answers to questions compiled in the form of a questionnaire or tasks on separate cards (they are distributed during the activity to the children of the inner circle).

While moving in a circle, children communicate and discuss the task at hand. During the game, children manage to talk through several topics, trying to convince their interlocutor that they are right. We use this technique in lessons to discuss problem situations, which allows each student to take part in the educational process, alternately being in the role of a student and then in the role of a teacher. Using the “Carousel” technique, it is important for the teacher to plan a problem situation, prepare tasks that will allow them to apply the acquired knowledge, and also support children in defending their opinions.

• "Cluster"

The "Cluster" technique can be effective in the classroom. For example, in Russian language lessons on the topic "Parts of Speech," we build with children a certain diagram from different parts of speech. In this scheme, children include various parts of speech: noun, verb, adjective. The guys gather in subgroups, each small group gives a description of the selected part of speech, then the students jointly combine all parts of speech into a single whole, describe the characteristic features of each part of speech. This cluster construction allows students not only to graphically present their knowledge about parts of speech, but also gives them the opportunity to learn to think in a group, reason, express their assumptions and arguments.

• Puzzle method

This method promotes the development of coherent speech and the creation of a holistic picture. In first grade, we use this method to build logical chains in lessons about the world around us and mathematics. In subsequent grades, literature lessons can be used to work with a group of text fragments on a specific topic. The text is made up of fragments. After all groups have read their texts aloud, the texts of neighboring groups are repeated. This allows not only to develop communication skills in working in a group, but also stimulates attention, the ability to listen and reproduce what is heard, and increases the responsibility of students. This method can be used when teaching detailed and brief retelling.

Interactive training simultaneously solves several problems:

- develops communication skills, helps to establish emotional contacts between students;
- solves an information problem, since it provides students with the necessary information, without which it is impossible to implement joint activities;
- develops general educational skills (analysis, synthesis, goal setting, etc.), that is, ensures the solution of educational problems;
- provides an educational task, teaches to work in a team, to listen to other people's opinions.

CONCLUSION

Interactive technologies are a reliable tool for achieving personal success, allowing you to manage communication processes, influence the decision-making process and learn through practice. This is another important feature of interactive methods, so they can be widely used in the work of every teacher.

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